

Utilization and clinical outcomes of sacubitril/valsartan in Sudanese heart failure patients: A multicenter cross-sectional study

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Abstract

Sacubitril/valsartan (Sac/Val) is a cornerstone therapy for heart failure with reduced ejection fraction (HFrEF), yet its real-world use remains poorly described in Sudan. This multicenter, cross-sectional study aimed to evaluate Sac/Val utilization patterns and clinical outcomes among 170 Sudanese patients. The mean patient age was 61 years, and 77.6% of patients found Sac/Val unaffordable. Additionally, 92.4% lacked insurance coverage. Most patients (62.4%) were de novo users, 78.8% initiated Sac/Val at 50 mg BID, 71.8% underwent up-titration, and only 36.5% achieved the target dose of 200 mg BID. Notably, longer treatment duration was significantly associated with higher hospitalization rates ($p = 0.003$), while achieving the target dose correlated with improved ejection fraction ($p = 0.045$). Despite guideline-based initiation and titration, target dose achievement remains suboptimal. Socioeconomic barriers predominate, limiting treatment optimization. These findings highlight an urgent need for policymakers to integrate Sac/Val into national insurance programs and improve its affordability.

Keywords

sacubitril/valsartan, heart failure, drug utilization, clinical outcomes, Sudan

Introduction

Heart failure (HF) is a clinical condition characterized by the heart's inability to pump blood effectively to meet the metabolic demands of the body, resulting in fatigue, shortness of breath, and fluid retention (McDonagh et al. 2023). Currently, HF is a prevalent and growing public

health concern affecting about 26 million people worldwide across diverse socioeconomic and geographic backgrounds (Savarese and Lund 2017). Moreover, HF prevalence is projected to increase in the coming years. This projection relies on different factors, including aging populations and increasing rates of cardiovascular risk factors such as hypertension (HTN), diabetes (DM), and obesity.

Additionally, advances in medical care have led to increased survival rates among patients with cardiovascular diseases (Savarese and Lund 2017).

In heart failure with reduced ejection fraction (HFrEF) patients, guideline-directed medical therapy (GDMT) includes target or maximum tolerated doses of angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors (ACEIs), angiotensin receptor blockers (ARBs), or angiotensin receptor neprilysin inhibitors (ARNIs) with an ARB in combination with beta-blockers (BBs). Additionally, the therapeutic regimen may include mineralocorticoid receptor antagonists (MRAs), sodium-glucose co-transporter 2 (SGLT2) inhibitors, and ivabradine. These medications work synergistically to reduce HF-related symptoms, improve cardiac function, reduce hospitalization, and prolong survival in HFrEF patients (Malgie et al. 2023).

Sacubitril/valsartan (Sac/Val), an ARNi, represents a significant milestone in the management of HFrEF. It combines a neprilysin inhibitor with an ARB (Chen et al. 2021a). In various studies, sacubitril/valsartan has been shown to improve cardiac function and exercise capacity, reverse cardiac remodeling, and reduce the risk of cardiovascular death and hospitalization due to its dual activity in HFrEF patients. Sac/Val is highly recommended by the European Society of Cardiology (ESC) and the American College of Cardiology (ACC) guidelines to lower the risk of cardiovascular death and hospitalization in HFrEF patients who are still symptomatic after receiving treatment with ACEIs/ARBs, BBs, and MRAs (Vardeny et al. 2014). This recommendation was supported by strong data from the Prospective Comparison of Angiotensin-Nepri-lysin Inhibition with ACEI to Determine the Impact on Global Mortality and Morbidity in Heart Failure (PARADIGM-HF) study. This is a randomized, double-blind, and event-driven trial that compared sacubitril/valsartan with enalapril in 8442 patients with HFrEF. With a 20% decrease in the primary outcome, which is a composite of hospitalization for HF or death from cardiovascular causes, sacubitril/valsartan proved to be superior. Additionally, the rate of all-cause mortality was decreased with sacubitril/valsartan by 16% (relative risk reduction) (Zhang et al. 2022). Following this recommendation, several studies have been conducted around the world to address Sac/Val real-world activities and utilization. Sac/Val was introduced in Sudan in 2017; however, the documentation of Sac/Val in real-world clinical practice has not yet been clearly documented. This study aims to describe the utilization and clinical outcomes of Sac/Val in patients with HFrEF, using data from selected hospitals in Sudan.

Methods

Study design

This descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted at four hospitals with cardiac referral clinics located in Khartoum State, Sudan (e.g., Al-Shaab Teaching Hospital, Al-mawada Private Hospital, Ahmed Gasim Hospital–Bahri,

and Al-Bugaa Hospital–Omdurman), from February 2022 to May 2022.

Study population

The study included 170 consecutive patients who were above 18 years of age, diagnosed with HFrEF, and had been using Sac/Val for at least 3 months, with a documented ejection fraction (EF) $\leq 40\%$, as measured by echocardiography, and attending the cardiac referral clinics in the four hospitals at the time of the study. Patients who were severely ill and unable to be interviewed, patients who had severe renal impairment, and patients with volume depletion were excluded from the study.

The sample size for the study was calculated using the Cochran formula (1963) [$N = (Z^2 * p * q) / e^2$] (Richter 1963). Considering a confidence interval of 99%, an estimated population proportion of 0.5 (50%), and a level of precision of 0.1, the calculated sample size was found to be 167 participants. A total of 170 patients were enrolled in the study using convenience and snowball sampling.

Data collection tool

A structured questionnaire that was primarily in English, along with the patient's medical records, was used for data collection in the study. The questionnaire was translated into Arabic, and the face and content validity of the tool was ensured by the study's principal investigator. A pilot study involving 30 patients was conducted to ensure item comprehension, and validity of the questionnaire was also conducted.

The questionnaire comprised three parts: 1) demographic data (age, sex, marital status, health insurance, professional status, and education level); 2) clinical characteristics (symptoms of HF, EF pre- and post-initiation of Sac/Val, comorbidities, prior HF treatment before sacubitril/valsartan initiation); and 3) utilization and clinical outcomes of patients with Sac/Val (duration of use, starting dose, and highest dose prescribed). Other sections included the availability and suitability of its cost and hospitalization status. In this study, we define the starting and target doses based on ESC guidelines on HF 2021 (McDonagh et al. 2021); hospitalization was defined as any admission due to HF or other causes.

Statistical analysis

Data were entered into a computer and analyzed using the IBM SPSS software package version 20.0 (Armonk, NY: IBM Corp.). Descriptive statistics were reported using numbers and percentages. One-way ANOVA and post hoc analysis were used to test the association between patient factors and clinical outcomes.

Ethical approval

This study adhered to the ethical guidelines of the 1975 Declaration of Helsinki and was approved by the Medical

Ethical Committee – Ministry of Health – Khartoum State (Serial Number: KMOH-REC-2022-NO.44). Written informed consent was obtained from all eligible participants, along with assurances of data privacy and anonymity.

Results

This study included a total of 170 HFrEF patients treated with Sac/Val. The cohort was predominantly male, 102 (60%), with a mean age of 61.07 ± 11.3 years, and 90 (52.9%) of participants clustered in the age group of 60 years and above. Hypertension, 102 (60%), and diabetes, 83 (48.8%), were the most commonly reported comorbidities. Baseline treatment analysis showed that 40 patients (23.6%) used ACEIs, 38 (22.4%) used ARBs, 59 (34.7%) used BBs, 46 (27.1%) used MRAs, and 43 of them (25.3%) used diuretics, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Socio-demographic characteristics and comorbidities of HF patients (n = 170).

Characteristics	Frequency (%)
Gender	
Male	102 (60)
Female	68 (40)
Age	
< 40	7 (4.1)
40–60	73 (42.9)
≥ 60	90 (52.9)
Age in years (Mean ± (SD))	61.07 ± (11.3)
Co-morbidities	
Hypertension	102 (60)
Diabetes mellitus	83 (48.8)
Renal problems	9 (5.3)
Thyroid disorders	5 (2.9)
Prostate disorders	3 (1.8)
Others	7 (4.1)
Heart failure medication prior to Sac/Val	
Angiotensin converting enzyme inhibitors (ACEIs)	40 (23.6)
Angiotensin receptor blockers (ARBs)	38 (22.4)
β-blockers (BBs)	59 (34.7)
Mineralocorticoids receptors antagonists (MRAs)	46 (27.1)
Diuretics	43 (25.3)

In terms of Sac/Val use, most of the study participants, 138 (81.2%), reported using the medication for 1–5 years, approximately 106 (62.4%) were using it de novo, and 134 (78.8%) reported starting with 50 mg BID. Additionally, nine (5.3%) started with 200 mg BID, while 27 (15.9%) of the study cohort started with 100 mg BID. With respect to dosing details, approximately 122 (71.8%) of patients had dose titrations throughout the therapeutic period. Approximately one-third, 62 (36.5%), of patients achieved the target dose of 200 mg BID, and 73 (42.9%) achieved 100 mg BID. However, despite the titration process, 35 (20.6%) of the participants tolerated a dose of 50 mg BID. Regarding socioeconomic barriers, 132 (77.6%) of participants reported that Sac/Val was “very expensive,” and 157 (92.4%) lacked insurance coverage. This is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Sac/Val utilization and prescribing patterns of Sac/Val (n = 170).

Characteristic	Frequency (%)
<1 year	29 (17.1)
1–5 year	138 (81.2)
>5 year	3 (1.8)
Duration of Sac/Val use in years (Mean ± (SD))	2.1 ± (1.5)
Initiation pattern of Sac/Val	
De novo	106 (62.4%)
Previous use of ACEIs	36 (21.1%)
Previous use of ARBs	35 (20.6%)
Starting dose of Sac/Val	
50 mg BD	134 (78.8)
100 mg BD	27 (15.9)
200 mg BD	9 (5.3)
Dose titration	
Titrated	122 (71.8)
Not titrated	48 (28.2)
Max. dose received	
50 mg (BD)	35 (20.6)
100 mg (BD)	73 (42.9)
200 mg (BD)	62 (36.5)
Availability of Sac/Val	
Always available	77 (45.3)
Sometimes available	93 (54.7)
Cost of Sac/Val	
Suitable	2 (1.2)
Expensive	36 (21.2)
Very expensive	132 (77.6)
Insurance coverage	
Yes	13 (7.6)
No	157 (92.4)

Table 3 presents a comparative analysis of clinical outcomes in patients treated with Sac/Val. Notably, the study revealed that patients with HF-related hospitalizations had significantly longer durations of Sac/Val use compared with those without hospitalizations (33.7 ± 15.9 months vs. 23.7 ± 16.9 months; mean difference: -9.98 , 95% CI: -16.62 to -3.34 ; $t = -2.97$, $p = 0.003$). However, there was no significant difference in the improvement of EF between the two groups (15.63 ± 6.73 vs. 14.98 ± 9.37 ; mean difference: -0.654 , 95% CI: -3.58 to 2.27 ; $t = -0.448$, $p = 0.656$). Additionally, achieving the target dose (200 mg BD) and maximum tolerated dose showed no significant association with hospitalization ($p > 0.05$), as shown in Table 4. Furthermore, a relationship was observed in EF improvement, with the target dose (200 mg BD) leading to the greatest benefit ($p = 0.045$), as shown in Table 5. Patients initiated de novo on Sac/Val tended to show greater EF improvement than those previously on an ACEI/ARB, though this was not statistically significant ($p = 0.128$), as shown in Table 6.

Discussion

Multiple studies have recognized the benefits of sacubitril/valsartan (Sac/Val) in improving ejection fraction (EF) in HFrEF patients, along with reducing hospitalization rates

Table 3. Clinical outcomes and dose response with Sac/Val.

Variable	Hospitalized (n = 30)	Not-hospitalized (n = 140)	Mean difference (95% CI)	t-Statistic (df)	P-value
	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)			
Duration of Sac/Val Use (months)	33.7 (15.9)	23.72 (16.9)	-9.98 (-16.62, -3.34)	-2.97 (168)	0.003
EF difference before and after Sac/Val	15.63 (6.73)	14.98 (9.37)	-0.654 (-3.58, 2.27)	-0.448 (168)	0.656

Table 4. Association between target dose achievement of Sac/Val 200 and HF-related hospitalizations.

Variable	Hospitalized (n = 30)	Not-hospitalized (n = 140)	X ² statistic (df)	P-value
Target dose of 200 mg BD achieved				
YES	10 (16.1)	52 (83.9)		
NO	20 (18.5)	88 (81.5)	0.155 (1)	0.694
Maximum tolerated dose reached				
50 mg BD	6 (17.1)	29 (82.9)	0.222 (2)	0.895
100 mg BD	14 (19.2)	59 (80.8)		
200 mg BD	10 (16.1)	52 (83.9)		

Table 5. Relationships between EF difference and maximum tolerated dose reached.

Variable	Highest dose received			F-statistic (df)	P-value
	50 mg BD (n = 34)	100 mg BD (n = 73)	200 mg BD (n = 61)		
	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)		
EF difference before and after Entresto	11.9 (8.98)	15.6 (9.06)	16.1 (8.55)	3.213 (2,165)	0.045

Table 6. Association between initiation pattern of Sac/Val and EF difference.

Variable	Commenced Sac/Val therapy de novo (n = 106)	Previously on ACEi/ARB (n = 64)	Mean difference (95% CI)	t-Statistic (df)	P-value
	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)			
EF difference before and after Sac/Val	15.9 (8.52)	13.75 (9.53)	2.155 (0.63, 4.94)	-1.528 (168)	0.128

and cardiovascular mortality (Greene et al. 2021; Aşkın and Tanrıverdi 2022; Oh et al. 2022; Sakhamuri et al. 2023). The PARADIGM-HF trial strongly supported the use of Sac/Val; however, discrepancies exist between clinical trial results and real-world utilization parameters. To address these differences and take into account the heterogeneous nature of HF, this is the first real-world study from Sudan aimed at describing the utilization of Sac/Val and its clinical outcomes in patients with HFrEF, based on data from four hospitals and including an assessment of Sac/Val dosing patterns and up-titration strategies.

In this study, males predominated, and the high comorbidity burden aligns with global HFrEF trends (McMurray et al. 2014; Wachter et al. 2020; Chen et al. 2021b), although the lower male proportion (60% vs. 79% in PARADIGM-HF) may reflect demographic and healthcare access differences specific to Sudan (McMurray et al. 2014).

Regarding Sac/Val dosing patterns, the majority of participants (78.8%) started at an initial dose of 50 mg (24/26 mg) BID. This finding is consistent with multiple studies conducted in China, Germany, and other countries, which reported that most participants initiated Sac/Val in line with guideline recommendations (Wachter et al. 2019; Wachter et al. 2020; Chen et al. 2021b; McDonagh et al. 2021). However, a notable contrast was observed in

a study from Saudi Arabia, where only 34% of patients initiated Sac/Val as de novo therapy compared to 62.4% in our cohort, highlighting differences in clinical practice between the two settings (Badreldin et al. 2023). Additionally, 15.9% and 5.3% of our study participants started sacubitril/valsartan at 100 mg (49/51 mg) BID and 200 mg (97/103 mg) BID, respectively. This variation may be attributed to prior use of high-dose ACEIs or ARBs with suboptimal outcomes before switching to Sac/Val.

For patients with HFrEF, morbidity and mortality are reduced with target doses of key therapeutic agents. As per current guidelines, Sac/Val should be titrated to a target dose of 200 mg BID if tolerated (McDonagh et al. 2021). Notably, 71.8% of study participants were up-titrated, while 28.2% remained on the initial starting dose. The proportion of patients who underwent up-titration was higher than in previous reports (Wachter et al. 2020; Chen et al. 2021b). However, despite these efforts, only 36.5% of participants achieved the target dose of 200 mg BID, while 20.6% tolerated a dose of 50 mg BID. This variation in titration success and the relatively low rate of reaching the target dose may reflect the real-world complexity of managing HFrEF, where patients are often frailer, more clinically complex, and burdened with multiple comorbidities compared to the relatively healthier participants

enrolled in the PARADIGM-HF study (Maggioni et al. 2013; Wachter et al. 2020; Chen et al. 2021b). These findings highlight the need for individualized treatment strategies that account for guideline-directed goals while considering patient-specific factors such as tolerability and comorbidity burden.

The relationship between Sac/Val therapy and clinical outcomes in Sudanese patients illustrates both the promise and challenges of managing HFrEF in real-world settings. The observation that patients with HF-related hospitalizations had longer durations of Sac/Val use (33.7 vs. 23.7 months, $p = 0.003$) likely reflects the fact that these individuals had more advanced or refractory disease requiring prolonged therapy. Hospitalized patients may also face external factors influencing treatment duration, such as medication availability, adherence challenges, cost, and lack of insurance coverage. Sacubitril/valsartan, though effective, is a high-cost medication, particularly in resource-constrained settings like Sudan, which may limit long-term use. In this study, 92.4% of participants reported lacking insurance coverage. Numerous studies have shown that high drug costs can impede adherence and negatively affect clinical outcomes, including hospitalization rates (Martens et al. 2018; Johnson et al. 2022). Importantly, the comparable EF improvements between hospitalized and non-hospitalized patients (15.63% vs. 14.98%, $p = 0.656$) reinforce Sac/Val's consistent efficacy in improving cardiac function, even in patients with severe disease. These modest EF gains are consistent with results from the PARADIGM-HF trial (McMurray et al. 2014), supporting the drug's utility across diverse populations.

The observed disconnect between EF improvement and hospitalization underscores a key challenge in HF management: while EF reflects cardiac function, it does not capture real-world barriers that contribute to hospitalization. In this study, 77.6% of participants described Sac/Val as very expensive, and 92.4% lacked insurance coverage – barriers that likely contribute to poor adherence and delayed care-seeking behavior, regardless of the drug's clinical efficacy (Khera et al. 2019). This may explain why achieving the target dose of 200 mg BID was associated with greater EF improvement ($p = 0.045$) but not with a reduction in hospitalization rates ($p > 0.05$). Optimal dosing alone may be insufficient to improve outcomes if patients cannot afford the medication or struggle to access care. To improve outcomes in such contexts, HF guidelines must address not only pharmacologic goals but also practical challenges, such as medication cost and healthcare access, particularly in countries like Sudan where these issues are prevalent (Heidenreich et al. 2022).

Patients who started Sac/Val de novo showed a trend toward greater EF improvement than those previously treated with ACEIs or ARBs, although the difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.128$). According to the latest guidelines, early initiation of Sac/Val may enhance cardiac function (Heidenreich et al. 2022). However, in resource-limited settings, where cost and accessibility

constrain prescribing decisions, timely initiation of Sac/Val is often unfeasible. Clinicians may be forced to prioritize high-risk patients for Sac/Val therapy, potentially delaying its use until later stages, which may inadvertently contribute to recurrent hospitalizations and disease progression.

The main strengths of this study include its contribution to the understanding of HFrEF management in Sudan – a region underrepresented in global cardiovascular literature – and its analysis of socioeconomic barriers to achieving optimal Sac/Val dosing. These insights can inform policymakers and support the inclusion of Sac/Val in national health insurance schemes to improve access.

Nevertheless, the study had several limitations. The sample size was relatively small, given the recent introduction and high cost of Sac/Val in Sudan, which limits its use among many patients. The study design was prospective, as retrospective analysis was impractical due to the lack of electronic medical records and consistent documentation in cardiac referral centers. Furthermore, difficulty retrieving key baseline parameters such as NYHA class, BMI, systolic blood pressure, and serum creatinine limited the ability to assess associations between these variables, Sac/Val dosing, EF changes, and hospitalization status.

Conclusion

This study describes the utilization of sacubitril/valsartan (Sac/Val) and its clinical outcomes in HFrEF patients in Sudan. Our findings show that most patients initiated Sac/Val at the recommended starting dose and underwent up-titration, although only one-third reached the target dose. Nevertheless, EF improved across all dosing strategies, with patients who initiated Sac/Val de novo showing better EF gains than those who switched from ACEIs or ARBs, though the difference was not statistically significant. These results underscore the importance of early initiation and careful dose titration to optimize therapeutic outcomes. Moreover, the study highlights substantial barriers to effective HF management. Most patients encountered difficulties accessing and adhering to Sac/Val therapy due to high costs and limited insurance coverage, which restricted long-term use and may have worsened clinical outcomes. Although Sac/Val consistently improved EF, socioeconomic constraints remained major obstacles to treatment success. Improving access through national insurance integration and cost reduction is crucial for advancing HF care in Sudan. Future research should include larger, multicenter studies to further assess the real-world impact of Sac/Val and address accessibility issues in resource-limited environments.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: This study adhered to the ethical guidelines of the 1975 Declaration of Helsinki and was approved by the Medical Ethical Committee-Ministry of Health-Khartoum State (Serial Number:(KMOH-REC-2022-NO.44). A written informed consent was obtained from all eligible participants, along with assurance of the privacy and anonymity of data.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Author contributions

A.E. Mohamed, T.K. Mohamed, B.A. Yousef and K.O. Ahmed involved in study concept and design, analysed and interpreted the data, had full access to all of the data in the study, and took responsibility for the integrity of the data and the accuracy of the data analysis. A.E. Mohamed, Y.W. Kassab and K.O. Ahmed acquired data. All authors contributed to the drafting and editing of the article and have granted their approval of the submitted manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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